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ADAPTATION OF FOREIGN STUDENTS TO THE UKRAINIAN EDUCATIONAL STANDARDS

According to the Bologna Process of 1998-1999, Ukraine reformed its educational system thus adapting it to the European Union standards while International students been one of the main components in the process of every university development as It enhances its credibility both in the home country and abroad.

Currently, Ukrainian educational system is undergoing considerable change in different areas. One of them is International students training and adaptation which is a significant factor in the formation of every nation as an equal partner in the world educational space. Ukrainian universities have been making an effort to create an international learning environment since 1991 [3].

Some of the adaptation problems encountered by foreign students in Ukraine can be divided into four groups with the necessary help required to ease the adaption of foreign students to the Ukrainian education standards [4].

1) Linguistic help: This type of help involves the studying the language of the host country in this case the Ukrainian language as such it is important to help the foreign student study intensively and also identify the ones who need additional training in studying the language, significant attention must be paid to the material devoted to the history and culture of the host country as well.

2) Legal help: Different types of legal assistance are in form of advice and educating the foreign students which are necessary for the prevention of delinquent behavior of foreign students. A major role in this kind of work belongs to the international departments, which should provide students with a minimum of legal knowledge and consult them on controversial issues which would help foreign not to get into troubles with the law of the host country.

3) Social-pedagogical help: This involves when developing a set of pedagogical measures aimed at the successful adaptation of foreign students, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the process of socio-cultural adaptation takes place in several stages, for example there are stages such as social and

cultural adaptation: "honeymoon stage" which is at the beginning of training of the foreign student and it is characterized by some euphoria about the fact that the student justified the hopes of his relatives and entered the high school, while the second is the "cultural shock" which is stays through the second and third years, while finally "stabilization" the senior year which is the final year of the foreign student.

4) Psychological help: This is especially important at the initial stages of the "honeymoon" and cultural shock. The task of this is to help the foreign students to orient himself in the surrounding situation to avoid a trap of "deceived hopes", to develop a system of values that will help him or her to better adapt to the new environment [2].

For the successful adaptation of foreign students in to the Ukrainian educational system, it is necessary to build an educational process taking into account ethno pedagogical concepts to effectively include students in the learning process, the teacher needs to do the following: take into account the age, religious, social and other affiliations of students; stimulate the motivational sphere; provide independence; create language situations that are as close to reality as possible; raise questions on topics that are interesting to this audience; objectively evaluate the results of independent activities of students considering their individual characteristics, form the cognitive need of a foreign student [5].

It is also important to note that social and psychological adaptation of foreign students is the key acquisition determinant of Ukrainian cultural field and the factor of favorable and efficient educational adaption for foreign students in Ukrainian educational standards [1].

The training of foreign students in Ukraine which helps the adaptation of the foreign students is one of the most effective forms of cultural and scientific cooperation that contributes to strengthening the authority of Ukraine in the international arena being a source of additional funding for education. Every year, foreign citizens come to study at higher educational institutions in Ukraine. These foreign students usually come from a society that differs from the European countries by their customs, traditions, legislation, world outlook, and religion. After entering the new environment, students encounter not only language problems but also psychological ones as they try to adapt to their new surroundings in Ukraine.

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АДАПТАЦІЯ СТУДЕНТІВ-ІНОЗЕМЦІВ ДО УКРАЇНСЬКИХ ОСВІТНІХ СТАНДАРТІВ

Тенденція швидкого збільшення кількості іноземних студентів, які приїжджають в Україну на навчання, вимагає нових підходів до освіти та регулювання міграційних процесів для забезпечення адаптації іноземних студентів у міжнародному освітньому секторі. На жаль, іноземні студенти мають багато труднощів при адаптації до Українських освітніх стандартів, зумовлених багатьма факторами.

***Ключові слова:** іноземні студенти, психологічна адаптація, педагогічна українська освітня система.*

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The trend of rapid increase in the number of international students who come to Ukraine to study requires new approaches to education and regulation of migration processes to ensure foreign student adaptation in the international education sector, unfortunately foreign students have a lot of difficulty in adapting to the Ukrainian educational standards due to multiple factors.

***Key words:** foreign students, psychological adaptation, pedagogical, Ukrainian educational system.*